

Common Sense Leadership in the Example of Turkish Political Leader Devlet Bahçeli

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Abstract—Peace diplomacy is the most important international tool to maintain peace all over the World. This study consists of three parts. In the first part, the leadership of Devlet Bahçeli, leader of the Nationalist Movement Party, will be introduced as a tool of peace communication and peace management. Also, in this part, peace communication will be explained by the peace leadership traits of Devlet Bahçeli, who is one of the efficient political leaders representing the concepts of compromise and agreement on different sides of politics. In the second part of study, it is aimed to analyze Devlet Bahçeli's leadership within the frame of peace communication and the final part of this study is about creating an original public communication model for public diplomacy based on Devlet Bahçeli as an example. As a result, the main purpose of this study is to develop an original peace communication model including peace modules, peace management projects, original dialogue procedures and protocols exhibited in the policies of Devlet Bahçeli. The political leadership represented by Devlet Bahçeli inspires political leaders to provide peace communication. In this study, principles and policies of peace leadership of Devlet Bahçeli will be explained as an original model on a peace communication platform.

Keywords—Dialogue management, public diplomacy, peace diplomacy, peace leadership.

I. INTRODUCTION

DEVLET Bahçeli, President of the Nationalist Movement Party, has introduced a model that is identified his name in Turkish politics with his strong communication skills, high representation and political mastery. The most important feature of the Devlet Bahçeli Model is the common sense leadership he has introduced to Turkish politics. The common sense leadership of Devlet Bahçeli is the formation of a political canon by transforming the ability to present a capacity for peace, dialogue, reconciliation, cooperation and collaboration into a political formula the eyes of public. "One of the most influential features of the Devlet Bahçeli System (School) is the political ombudsmanship he presents. Dr. Devlet Bahçeli, as a political ombudsman, has been the most reliable and prominent leader in overcoming political disagreements in society and overcoming bottlenecks. He has combined political ombudsmanship with social communication leadership and which in many cases, has emerged as a social demand. Common sense leadership is the resolution of political and social problems, not only through

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political, but also humanitarian and conscientious leadership means.

Devlet Bahçeli has developed a definition of conscientious leadership in order to overcome social problems, and this recognition has brought a strong meaning to the human values with the humanitarian values he has implemented in his own political life. It is recommended that political leaders and diplomats, who undertake the responsibilities of mediating international conflicts, should consider the model of Devlet Bahçeli as a conflict-eliminating peaceful leader. Devlet Bahçeli's commonsense leadership has played a key role in the establishment and protection of the People's Alliance in Turkish politics, as well as recognition as a strong political alliance that determined what is it to establish an alliance.

II. DEVLET BAHÇELI'S LEADERSHIP MODEL

A. Basic Categories of Devlet Bahçeli's Common Sense Leadership

Leader of the Nationalist Movement Party Dr. Devlet Bahçeli has established a model that is identified with his name, along with the initiatives he has taken in the basic categories that determine common sense leadership in Turkish Politics. Common sense should be defined as: It is a central sense, towards which, all impressions converge and unite in one sentiment -the desire for the truth [1]. Basic categories of Devlet Bahçeli's common sense leadership can be listed as follows:

1. Evaluation of Balance Point Factors in Political Platform

One of the aspects where Devlet Bahçeli stands out in Turkish politics and takes the initiative leadership is his playmaker leadership. Playmaker leadership is a leadership that can demonstrate to be acting on political grounds in correct planning, where political conditions are ambiguous with disagreements and political consensus. The playmaker aspect in politics is the ability to place balance point factors to eliminate uncertainty in politics, in a setting where political movements are weakened and uncertainties increase, relations among political actors become more complex. One of the most successful aspects in Devlet Bahçeli's playmaker leadership is the ability to determine the balance point factors and put them into practice and on-going processes. Furthermore, Devlet Bahçeli's ability is an important leadership features also in the solution of international conflicts and resolution of international disputes. The balance factors that Devlet Bahçeli has brought to Turkish political life can be listed as follows:

a) Ability to Determine the Balance Point of Uncertainty and Rewarding Uncertainty

One of the biggest political features and abilities of Devlet Bahçeli is the achievement to determine the balance point of uncertainty. It is important to define the balance point of uncertainty as concerns the elimination of political uncertainties and determination of correct point to operate political channels at the right time. Balance point of uncertainty is the determination of correct interventions in order to create an innovation and development from uncertainty, taking into account the situation in which political uncertainty develops, the actors of this uncertainty and the conditions that feed ambiguity. For instance, in an environment where politics becomes uncertain and complex, creating an innovational direction that will eliminate the uncertainty through balancing should be drawn as destination by separating all solutions to one side and the conditions forming the uncertainty to the other. This innovation will also be a key starting point for political consensus. First of all, Devlet Bahçeli has political ability to create an innovation from uncertainty. Meanwhile, creating innovation from uncertainty is also a situation that overcomes political deadlock. For instance, in Turkish Grand National Assembly, blockage of parliamentary activities on any issue and failure of parliamentary activities is one of the political uncertainties. Devlet Bahçeli interferes with politics at times when the deadlocks and conflicts have already turned troublesome and into a crisis. In such cases, Devlet Bahçeli sets a political model to bring innovation in order to resolve political conflicts, thereby resolving deadlocks. When politics is blocked and uncertainty has become a communication process, it is one of the most defining features of common sense leadership to create an innovation point in order to be active and balance uncertainty; to make policy in that era, Devlet Bahçeli undertakes initiative leadership to familiarize this point and reconstruct politics. It is important to define the concept of being a balance point which has been introduced by Devlet Bahçeli to the concept of common sense leadership.

The main features of the “Rewarding Uncertainty” concept that Devlet Bahçeli offers the Turkish political arena are as follows:

- Rewarding Uncertainty, when politics become uncertain, is the correct position of categories of uncertainty. Devlet Bahçeli excellently identifies the basic categories of areas that create uncertainty in Turkish politics.
- Rewarding Uncertainty means interaction between categories that create uncertainty and correct determination of categories. Devlet Bahçeli determines the interaction among basic uncertainty categories that shape politics and makes the right referral about how these relations affect the existing uncertainty. This is also a political chess mastership.
- Rewarding uncertainty is mastership to eliminate grey zone and gossip areas that create uncertainty. Meanwhile, uncertainty creates gossip areas that influence the system; these areas are defined as the grey zone of politics. Devlet Bahçeli reduces the impact of grey areas, identifying the

correct communication themes so that rumors will not affect or do any harm to the system by determining the correct areas spreading the buzz in politics. One of the most important areas of common sense leadership that Devlet Bahçeli provided to Turkish politics is to disable gossip mechanisms and perform correct actions by resolving rumor channels.

- One of the political assets pertaining to Rewarding the Uncertainty is to be able to undertake a political leadership role related to determining the issues where the society is likely to become troubled with and resolving this problem. Political uncertainty can also lead to social conflicts. Devlet Bahçeli undertakes leadership and prevents transformation of uncertainty into conflict by determining the right point, in that political uncertainty transforms social uncertainty. This is a feature that is one of the most important aspects of rewarding uncertainty and identifies with common sense leadership. Meanwhile, this quality of Devlet Bahçeli is an important point to guide international leaders. One of the areas where social conflicts are most affected is that of political uncertainties and disputes between political actors. Devlet Bahçeli identifies the right point where political uncertainty is transformed into social uncertainty, taking the leadership at that point and preventing uncertainty from turning into conflict. One of the important communication skills that Devlet Bahçeli has brought to Turkish politics is the political ability to correctly determine channels from which the uncertainties spread out and to take appropriate measures to prevent the spread. It is one of the communication skills about the common sense leadership of Devlet Bahçeli to understand uncertainty’s circulation area correctly and to be able to interfere politically at critical positions in these areas and take the initiative.

B. Devlet Bahçeli’s Balancing Moderator Leadership

One of the most important political balance factors that Devlet Bahçeli brought to Turkish politics is his balancing moderator leadership. Devlet Bahçeli’s political moderation is a strong negotiating point for resolving important political conflicts and resolving disputes. “The motivation to provide mediation arises because the third party sees the ongoing conflict and its effects on civilians as creating a humanitarian emergency of sufficient magnitude to require some actor to do something about the conflict” [2]. At this point, Devlet Bahçeli’s Moderator Leadership is one of the important issues to be examined in regard to common sense leadership. Devlet Bahçeli’s balanced moderator leadership is to gain the basic balance areas that will provide consensus in Turkish politics as playmaker leadership. “Probably the most common question raised about mediation (both domestic and international) is how a party should go about identifying a suitable mediator. We would rephrase that as two slightly different questions: (1) how does one go about locating candidates for a mediator role, and (2) how does one select a mediator who is appropriate for the dispute?” [3]. Transformation of balance areas in politics into a playmaker field that will lead society and in favor of

society is also a balancing moderation. These balancing moderation features that brought by Devlet Bahçeli to Turkish politics can be listed as follows:

a) The most important reflection of Devlet Bahçeli's balancing moderator ability as a leader of common sense can be seen in the fact that he has introduced the definition of balancing leadership to politics and that he has already managed to let himself be accepted as the strongest representative of this type of leadership. Balance leadership in the context of moderation, in cases where differences in politics turn into a non-solution and non-alternative concepts, is to be able to offer alternatives with a strong leadership approach and correct political leadership, and also to establish the fact that he is decisive in alternative approaches as a political leader and the dominant power to reach consensus for the realization of these alternatives. One of the biggest contributions of Devlet Bahçeli to Turkish political life and to common sense leadership features is to identify different alternatives and influence the politic process as a powerful moderator in the realization of these alternatives. It is one of the strongest communication concepts of common sense leadership, to emphasize the fact that politics has alternatives and to exhibit a political leadership that will be a critical body for these alternative concepts. The four items that determine balancing moderation brought by Devlet Bahçeli to common sense leadership are as follows:

1. One of the most distinctive features of the balancing moderator leadership introduced by Devlet Bahçeli to Turkish political life that can act as a guide in the solution of the disputes in the world is the connective leadership, which is a reflection of the diplomatic ability in international relations to Turkish politics. Connective leadership means that in a society where a political leader lives and leads, he can combine traditions, procedures, legal processes, and culture and customs that hold society together in a resolute leadership style, with his strong efforts in political life and society as a guardian of formal mechanisms and traditions. Leadership in this regard can be defined as connective leadership in political life. One of the most important leadership characteristics of Devlet Bahçeli on political life and common sense leadership is achieved with this type of leadership. Connective leadership is a strong line of leadership in the advocacy of values and traditions that are peculiar to a given society.
2. Another feature of Balancing Moderators is that they have a key reputation and prestige to place mechanisms which balance the system, so this feature can be defined as "provider leadership". Provider leadership is the ability to open key channels of politics and to provide these channels to the field of society and politics.

Devlet Bahçeli has the ability and leadership that provide solutions to implementations of various channels to solution-oriented, complementary and descriptive mechanisms.

3. The rhetoric leadership introduced by Devlet Bahçeli to Turkish politics is of strategic importance in terms of

triggering the system-balancing mechanisms. In this point, the concept of rhetoric leadership is not just about being a good and powerful preacher but about reaching the socially strategic and strong areas through this trait in a given society. For instance, Devlet Bahçeli has a strong rhetoric leadership in Turkish politics about development of intellectual context and use of cultural values that will mobilize intellectual leaders. As a political leader, he has considered cultural values and cultural codes as a part of common sense leadership and placed his ideational life to the center of his rhetoric. Besides, Devlet Bahçeli is one of the most effective political leaders in Turkish sports life and for Turkish youth. When evaluated from these perspectives, Devlet Bahçeli is one of the most powerful political leaders of Turkish political life in terms of magnitude and effectiveness of the area he addressed as a rhetoric leader.

4. One of the most important features of the balancing moderation brought by Devlet Bahçeli to Turkish political life is character leadership. Devlet Bahçeli has a unique characteristic leadership along with his own temperament and characteristics. Characteristic leadership is the formation of a reputable leadership in society and political life with his unique characteristics of a political leader.

In regards to his political career and his contribution to Turkish politics, Devlet Bahçeli's political attitudes, practices and approaches offer to present his unique political models in the country's politics. Political Invitation Leadership is one of these models.

C. Political Invitation Leadership

Devlet Bahçeli's invitation leadership and political ability about social invitations constitute the most important levels of common sense leadership. Invitation leadership is the recognition of a message delivered by a political leader to a community as an invitation by its addressee, and the transformation of the leader's message power into an invitation leadership force. One of the rarest leaders in Turkish politics, who has captured the invitation power with his messages and undertaken the role of invitation leadership, is Dr Devlet Bahçeli, President of the Nationalist Movement Party.

Herein, in order to better define common sense leadership, it is necessary to understand the moment where message power turns into invitation leadership power. This is also a key moment that determines leadership. Message power is the power of a political leader to mobilize mechanisms to enable society to be accepted in the society, and the ability of a political leader to share a social and political approach with society about a particular issue. On the other hand, invitation communication leadership is the transformation of the initiation of a political leader on a particular social issue or the political attitude he/she develops on a particular political issue into the leadership of a particular social movement by society as the fundamental approach that describes this social or political issue. Meanwhile, it is acceptance of the political attitude and approach of the leader as a starting point and basic leadership for a social movement.

Dr. Devlet Bahçeli, along with Turkish President Recep Tayyip Erdoğan, are two of the most effective leaders with regard to invitation leadership. At this point, to better understand common sense leadership, as in the case of Devlet Bahçeli, eight basic categories that determine invitation leadership should be elucidated.

1. Invitation Leadership is a Political Invitation Communication Skill: Invitation leadership is one of the most essential invitation communication skills for common sense leadership. One of the most important factors that makes Dr. Devlet Bahçeli strong in Turkish politics is his political ability in regard to invitation communication. One of the most important features that make invitation communication a strong element in political communication is the transformative sharing of the invitation. This point has a distinctive feature within the scope of common sense leadership. Transformational sharing of an invitation by a leader is to have a transformative effect of a subject that a political leader addresses within a given society as a call within the framework of rhetoric. Transformational effect is that the message which a political leader presents to society on any issue is the reference point for that society to create a social initiative on the issue. One of the most important achievements of President of Nationalist Movement Party, Dr. Devlet Bahçeli is his ability to find these reference points and to connect them with society. The messages that Devlet Bahçeli presents to society about various issues are accepted and adopted by society, and have the power to mobilize society. Society refers to the leadership of Devlet Bahçeli in developing a social movement about certain issues, and this reference eventually becomes a social and political model.
2. Invitation Leadership by Devlet Bahçeli offers Participatory Negotiation approach to Society: One of the main categories determining President of the Nationalist Movement Party, Dr. Devlet Bahçeli's invitation leadership is that it offers a participatory negotiation approach to society. Participatory Negotiation is the development of a negotiating framework that will improve the invitation force of a message which is accepted by society as an invitation and becomes an invitation communication. The development of the invitation force of a message by a political leader which is accepted as an invitation is the transformation of this invitation to a social model and the transformation into a model and framework that society develops itself with a high level of participation which the invitation provides. One of the most important achievements of invitation leadership by Devlet Bahçeli is transformation of invitation communication into participatory negotiation, transformation of this invitation by society itself into an initiative, and society's development of the negotiating channels to convert this initiative to broader social participation.
3. Devlet Bahçeli's Invitation Leadership Offering Strong Invitation-Based Mechanisms for Participation: One of

the strongest levels of the common sense leadership of President of the Nationalist Movement Party Dr. Devlet Bahçeli is that he has a leadership approach which offers strong response based on invitation for participation. This approach can be defined as "Spreading Representation" of the invitation. Spreading Representation means that the message of a political leader transformed into a social call captures the very attention of the addressee in the most powerful way, so that this call is responded to through the strongest channels by a given community. Devlet Bahçeli's call on society offers a powerful sharing to find the strongest and most critical responders who are interested in this invitation, and provide opportunity for responders to react to this invitation. Devlet Bahçeli's political mastery in this regard can be defined as the reciprocal power of his call and Devlet Bahçeli is the leader with the most effective representation in Turkish politics in terms of reciprocal power.

4. Devlet Bahçeli's Invitation Leadership and "Narration Troika": A basic characteristic of Devlet Bahçeli's invitation leadership is his ability to present effective figures and his persuasive narration that will gain a reaction from society to his social invitation. This initiative and power of Devlet Bahçeli in regards to invitation leadership can be defined as presenting effective narration, using compelling figures and choosing competent mechanisms; such that, in the case of Devlet Bahçeli, this trio of elements can be defined as "Narration Troika". Devlet Bahçeli's "Narration Troika" that consists of these three elements, is also an approach which will be a model for international common sense leadership. Finding the active figures and symbols for invitation in the community, bringing these figures together with society and choosing an effective mechanism, provides a strong sharing of social invitation that is identified with Devlet Bahçeli. Narration Troika is a model presented by Devlet Bahçeli to Turkish politics as a common sense leadership feature, and includes strong narrations that can be considered as common sense leadership in international relations.
5. Another political skill in perceiving the message presented by President of the Nationalist Movement Party Dr. Devlet Bahçeli to society as invitation leadership is "Movement power of invitation" in communication with society. One of Devlet Bahçeli's greatest contributions to Turkish politics, as a leader of common sense, is to create movement leaders for the use of this initiative by responders of a message to turn that message into an initiative in society and that these leaders accept Devlet Bahçeli as the natural leader of movement. In fact, this is the essence of the motto: "The leader of movement is Devlet Bahçeli". The power of a common sense leader to create initiative leaders who will act upon this invitation is one of the most important levels to create common sense leadership.
6. Devlet Bahçeli's other skill, as part of common sense leadership about invitation leadership, is that of providing

“Conscientious transformation of invitation”. When Dr. Devlet Bahçeli’s invitations that he presents to society on various issues are evaluated, in the adoption of these invitations by the society, it is seen that the areas where the messages presented in society are reciprocated and responded by the addressed group also point to some certain breaking points and these breaking points establish a type of conscientious-based partnerships in the community aiming at the establishment of a social revision and change. One of the most important common sense leadership features of Devlet Bahçeli is to find the breaking points that will achieve this conscientious partnership and transform these points into a social movement; these characteristics should be evaluated within the international relations system known as the Devlet Bahçeli Model. In terms of invitation communication, areas where social breakpoints transform into a conscientious partnership can be defined as transformation of invitation into a conscientious partnership; this transformation is one of the key common sense leadership features.

7. Another defining feature of Devlet Bahçeli’s invitation leadership is “apparent power of invitation”. Apparent power of invitation is, in a consensus process, to evaluate a social conflict area in which a political leader’s invitation for society gets the highest possible response. One of the greatest communication skills of Devlet Bahçeli within the scope of invitation leadership is his ability to turn conflict areas into areas of consensus. The invitation-leadership feature where this ability finds meaning is the apparent strength of the invitation. An invitation to the public by Devlet Bahçeli, presented by him and accepted by the target group in society, finds its most obvious angle, which then acts as a determining factor for the elimination of a conflict. One of the areas where President of the Nationalist Movement Party Devlet Bahçeli’s invitation communication is the strongest is his “expression sharing of invitation”. Another approach to Devlet Bahçeli’s model of common sense leadership is transformation of an invitation that is presented by the leader to society into a social attitude, and in the meantime, the transformation of this invitation into a social leadership that explains social sensitivities.

III. DEVLET BAHÇELI AS A POLITICAL OMBUDSMAN

Devlet Bahçeli has achieved a very respectable place in Turkish political life as an ombudsman.

“Political ombudsman is entitled to the powers, protection under the Act to make use of procedures, process, proceedings and practices appertaining to the post of ombudsman” [4].

Therefore, Devlet Bahçeli's common sense leadership needs to be examined given the characteristics of his Ombudsmanship. The ombudsman is the person providing the common sense climate with a supranational understanding by undertaking a reliable communication leadership among the parties of the dispute in the elimination of conflicts and

disagreements. Many times, Devlet Bahçeli has undertaken a mission to eliminate conflicts with the understanding of the need of continuation of the state's existence in the course of his political career. The main characteristics of Devlet Bahçeli as an ombudsman in Turkish politics as part of his common sense leadership are as follows:

1. Conflict Solver Leadership
2. The head of the Nationalist Movement Party, Dr Devlet Bahçeli, has taken a conflict solver position in terms of common sense leadership. Decisive leadership is the selection of the right actors to eliminate these conflicts by identifying the main conflict areas in political and social life and providing social support and acceptance in the process. “Shuttle diplomacy involves the President (or chair of subsidiary body, or a designated colleague) literally shuttling between each negotiating coalition” [5]. With his mastery and communication skills, Devlet Bahçeli exhibits one of the most powerful examples of anti-conflict/conflict solver leadership. “Broadly speaking, there are number of ways of managing international conflicts. Four different approaches to conflict management may be identified. These are (1) threats, use of force and competence, (2) deterrence, (3) adjudication, and (4) accommodation (e.g., negotiation and mediation) [6]. One of the greatest masteries of Devlet Bahçeli in political life is that he can choose the right actors to prevent conflicts, allowing them to be placed in the process and make the necessary evaluations.
3. The second important feature of Devlet Bahçeli as an ombudsman in Turkish politics is the concept of "Trust Flow Leadership" As an ombudsman, trust flow leadership stands for the creation of a kind of social corridor with the leadership power in eliminating the uncertainties, conflicts and conflict areas and maintaining domination on this corridor. Devlet Bahçeli also exhibits the “Trust Flow Leadership” feature, leading the way in social initiatives that affect the process and crisis management and ensure the flow of trust.
4. It is the skill of dialogue management that reinforces Devlet Bahçeli's prudence and common sense leadership and makes it more meaningful in the evaluation of the leader as a political ombudsman. Dialogue management is a characteristic that should be strong in a political leader, and influence the political sphere. Dialogue management is the transformation of a process that will open up and operate the dialogue channels of process management that will solve uncertainties in the political field, and other problems and allow society to gain dialogue leaders afterwards and prepare the ground for dialogue. This is also a political leadership understanding. The dialogue management exhibited by Devlet Bahçeli, leader of the Nationalist Movement Party, is a subject that can be considered as the Devlet Bahçeli Model. Thus, Bahçeli is a political ombudsman in Turkish politics with his mastery in dialogue management.
5. The political mastery of Devlet Bahçeli, as a political ombudsman in Turkish politics, also lies in his "Wisdom

in Dialogue Moderatorship". Dialogue moderators, in the process of a dialogue management, are the most effective channels and mechanisms to create a dialogue. They are also the people who have a binding leadership in the presence of important actors who need to participate in the process, especially at the activist level. One of the key elements of Devlet Bahçeli's ombudsman leadership in Turkish politics is his wise leadership and dominance over the actors as the moderator of dialogue. In the event of political or social uncertainty, there are several actors who are required to take action and are expected to manage the process. Devlet Bahçeli presents a political ombudsman character in the selection, evaluation and engagement of these actors, and presents his political charisma and wise leadership with his dominance over the actors.

6. In evaluating the impact of Devlet Bahçeli as an ombudsman on the process, the formula of "Having Superior Dialogue Initiative" should also be considered as the Devlet Bahçeli model, which means identifying the priorities and sensitivities of the parties of a dialogue process as an untouchable area and determining the act of action that can be chosen as a common mode of action as a result of the perspective drawn by these priorities and sensitivities. Devlet Bahçeli is the most effective representative of the national and spiritual values holding the Turkish nation together and his ability to determine the survival and future of the state as a model of social cohesion enables him to put this model to the act of expression to determine the common movement way with great success in the dialogue process. This act of expression is sometimes a rally that will provide a common exit; but in any case, it opens the doors of social dialogue.
7. One of the masteries of Devlet Bahçeli within the framework of being a real ombudsman lies in his ability to manage the dialogue in the "Interparty Dialogue Traffic" model. The most ideal way to settle disputes is to come together and discuss the debated areas with the related parties. Nowadays, the concept of diplomacy exists particularly to solve international disputes. Devlet Bahçeli is a political leader who has adapted the diplomacy carried out in international relations to Turkish politics and presents a model of Devlet Bahçeli Diplomacy. The most important feature of the Devlet Bahçeli's diplomacy is that it can take the solution step and present the formula of dialogue, even on the most cluttered and unresolved issues, and in the most clogged areas of politics. The right and timely political moves of Devlet Bahçeli are of great importance considering the solution of the many blockages of Turkish politics in the 2000s. The dialogue traffic between the parties means the planning of the negotiations of the representatives of the parties in the event of any disputes to arise. It is possible to make plans about who these representatives will be, how often they will discuss, which topics to discuss, which stage the new representatives will be involved in

the process, and the communication that the representatives will perform mutually in the process. Devlet Bahçeli is an effective leader who is able could carry out such a process of management in Turkey.

8. In the political and social ombudsman model of Devlet Bahçeli, the "Neutral Field Creation" power in the process of dialogue management is an important common-sense leadership feature of Devlet Bahçeli. This is because the most important feature to be considered among the parties is neutrality in the resolution of disagreements on both the international and national level to eliminate the uncertainties.

"Thus cultural mediators are not perceived as a neutral third side but rather are expected to operate for the sake of social justice in the community and for the sake of cultural sensitivity" [7].

Being and acting impartial is a very important process which needs to be carried out at equal distances for everyone, without causing any discrimination, taking transparent relations into account with objective principles. In particular, in order to eliminate conflicts and to prevent uncertainties, such neutrality characteristics must be put into the field and transformed into a form of communication. This area, which can also be called an impartial field, is the most effective field of action in terms of addressing problems and reaching an agreement.

President of the Nationalist Movement Party Devlet Bahçeli has established a platform of equilibrium and cooperation which would bring a relief to Turkish politics, and has also provided a facilitating dialogue model by establishing an objective field and an increase in his effectiveness as a political ombudsman. Sudden and strong decisions, which are effective mechanisms, are adapted into Turkish politics by Devlet Bahçeli, thus leading him to undertake common sense leadership in unexpected times.

9. Devlet Bahçeli's important communication success and supremacy as a political and social ombudsman lies in his leadership in his "Establishing Moderative Mechanism". The sobriety mechanism is to carry out the ombudsman process within the limits of being moderate; in other words, to define the characteristics of common sense leadership as the principles of mutual communication. When defining the common sense leadership presented by Devlet Bahçeli to Turkish politics as a communication model, these principles should be transformed into those that will draw the main framework of political negotiations and communication, as well as into accepted procedures by all people. These principles, which can be referred to as the sobriety mechanism are: Equity, survival, tradition, national consciousness, humanity, a conscientious future, commitment to cultural heritage and values, strong belonging to national values, dominance of technology, adherence to the state and leader, loyalty to values and values.
10. The Alliance Model, which is one of the important models that Devlet Bahçeli has introduced into Turkish politics, reinforces the emphasis on his common sense

leadership as a political ombudsman. "The process of forming an alliance is messy and complex, involving as it does at least two and perhaps many more already messy and complex organizations as partners and owners" [8]. In particular, "The People's Alliance" formed with the Justice and Development Party has an important role in bringing the concept of alliance into Turkish politics. Considering the future and the survival of the country and the nation, turning a common spirit and understanding into a common action for the benefit of the nation within the framework of the same basic principles and in line with the same values with certain political parties, constitutes the basis for an alliance. The formation of the alliance culture of Devlet Bahçeli and the role of alliance understanding in Turkish politics is another unique ombudsman quality belonging to him.

The establishment of the alliance culture as a model for Turkish political life is a great political mastery in the field of dialogue management in the Devlet Bahçeli Model, in which The People's Alliance (Cumhur İttifakı) is most important and principal projection in the field.

IV. CONCLUSION

President of the Nationalist Movement Party Devlet Bahçeli provided a model of leadership in Turkish politics and has been regarded as a balancing figure in overcoming uncertainties. Devlet Bahçeli has also managed to transform the political formulas he presented for the resolution of disputes into a political communication expansion area and has been recognized as the architect of the reconciliation and dialogue in Turkish society. Devlet Bahçeli, who has won trust and reliability as a political actor in politics with his leadership skills and the public trust exhibited to him by society -even from those who never vote for him- has already shown his power to determine the milestones of politics with his respectful representation. Devlet Bahçeli's communication and peaceful capabilities are also important to note in his being recognized as a common sense leader. The communication features, the unique rhetoric, the rostrum domination, the communication with society, the public and the initiatives launched by him on behalf of the people, and his relationship with arts, culture, literature, humor, sports as well as his having a communication established with the young generations have all together paved the way for him to become a leader of social communication. Combining common sense leadership with his own peaceful abilities, Devlet Bahçeli transformed his political skills into a political model and gained the support of society. The political leadership style and model of Devlet Bahçeli is one of a peace ombudsmanship, which can be a guide for the elimination of international disputes.

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